

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

Table S1. Ages and sexes of Rusty Blackbirds affixed with nano-transmitters at Observatoire d’oiseaux de Tadoussac, Québec (QC) and New England (NE) by year. At QC, ratios of adult (AHY) to immature (HY) and female (F) to male (M) were relatively even, but more adult females were tagged in NE than adult males. Nestlings were tagged in NE in 2022 and 2023 only, and could not be sexed (U is unknown).

Region	Year	AHY F	AHY M	HY F	HY M	HY U	U F	U
QC	2017	5	3	7	6	0	0	0
	2018	6	12	5	5	0	2	0
	2019	1	5	2	5	0	0	0
	2020	16	4	15	17	0	0	0
QC	Total	28	24	29	33	0	2	0
NE	2019	7	5	0	0	0	0	0
	2021	14	6	0	0	0	0	0
	2022	6	1	1	0	9	0	0
	2023	2	0	0	0	10	0	1
NE	Total	29	12	1	0	19	0	1
Total		57	36	30	33	19	2	1

Table S2. Models, burst intervals (seconds), estimated lifespans (days), and numbers of Lotek Avian NanoTag nano-transmitters affixed to Rusty Blackbirds at Observatoire d’oiseaux de Tadoussac, Québec (QC) and New England (NE) by year.

Site	Year	Model	Burst(sec)	Estimated Lifespan(days)	n
QC	2017	ANTC-M4-2	14.9	457	18
	2017	NTQB-4-2	19.9	515	3
	2018	ACT-521	13.0	179	20
	2018	ANTC-M4-2	14.9	457	4
	2018	NTQB-2	19.9	106	5
	2018	NTQB-4-2	5.3	254	1
	2019	ACT-521	13.0	179	13
	2020	ACT-521	13.0	179	7
	2020	NTQB2-4-2S	13.0	673	21
	2020	NTQB2-6-1	12.7	938	23
NE	2019	NTQB2-4-2S	5.9	364	6
	2019	NTQB2-4-2S	8.9	508	6
	2021	NTQB2-4-2S	8.9	508	18
	2021	NTQB2-4-2S-M	8.9	508	2
	2022	NTQB2-4-2S-M	8.9	508	17
	2023	NTQB2-4-2S-M	8.9	508	13

Table S3. Number of individual Rusty Blackbirds detected by individual Motus receivers, with latitude, longitude, and totals from each capture site (Observatoire d’oiseaux de Tadoussac, Québec (QC) and New England (NE). Receivers with one detection are not shown.

Receiver name	Prov/State	Latitude°N	Longitude°W	Total	QC	NE
Tadoussac2	QC	48.1591	-69.6623	64	64	0
Pointe Noire	QC	48.1232	-69.7168	61	61	0
Grève de Tadoussac	QC	48.1406	-69.719	31	31	0
Kamouraska	QC	47.5675	-69.8567	24	24	0
St-Denis-sur-Mer	QC	47.5154	-69.9502	23	23	0
Anse au Persil	QC	47.8756	-69.5503	19	19	0
St-Roch-des-Aulnaies	QC	47.3109	-70.1677	18	18	0
Newtowne Neck State Park, Compton	MD	38.2507	-76.702	15	8	7
Deer Pond Farm	CT	41.553	-73.5236	14	7	7
South Valley	NH	44.8716	-71.2254	14	2	12
Patuxent River Park	MD	38.7738	-76.7113	12	6	6
Cate's Hill	NH	44.5136	-71.1872	12	1	11
D'Estimauville	QC	46.843	-71.2111	12	12	0
Riviere-Ouelle	QC	47.4266	-70.0611	11	11	0
St. Andre Est (Kamouraska)	QC	47.704	-69.7007	11	11	0
Crystal Mtn	NH	44.9443	-71.2087	10	0	10
Interstate Fire Tower	DE	38.8015	-75.7205	8	6	2
Rushton Farm	PA	39.9842	-75.4892	8	4	4
D8C_2	PA	40.4045	-76.6825	8	4	4
Cap Tourmente	QC	47.0719	-70.7852	8	8	0
Pte-Moreault	QC	47.9571	-69.4765	8	8	0
Dameron Marsh	VA	37.7864	-76.3059	7	3	4
Blackwater NWR	MD	38.446	-76.0919	7	2	5
Poplar Island	MD	38.7569	-76.3845	7	0	7
Buck Run	PA	39.9415	-75.8077	7	4	3
Bluestem Farm	MD	39.2283	-75.9909	6	0	6
Bucktoe Preserve	PA	39.8209	-75.7221	6	1	5
Ned Smith Center	PA	40.5274	-76.9409	6	4	2
Tadoussac - roulotte	QC	48.1594	-69.6631	6	6	0
Langley AFB	VA	37.0987	-76.3551	5	3	2
Wellington WMA	MD	38.1576	-75.6173	5	4	1
Castleton View	VA	38.604	-78.109	5	1	4
DuPont Environmental Education Center	DE	39.7233	-75.5606	5	3	2
Marshlands 1	PA	40.1276	-75.769	5	3	2
Blue Marsh Lake SGL	PA	40.4107	-76.0796	5	4	1
PKR_salt_pannes	MA	42.7804	-70.8084	5	3	2
James River NWR	VA	37.2635	-77.1439	4	3	1
New Point Comfort	VA	37.3205	-76.2788	4	3	1
Buntings	MD	38.1385	-75.1889	4	3	1
Redden SF	DE	38.7421	-75.4146	4	1	3

Receiver name	Prov/State	Latitude°N	Longitude°W	Total	QC	NE
Patuxent Research Refuge	MD	39.0274	-76.7974	4	2	2
Norman G. Wilder WMA	DE	39.0341	-75.6415	4	3	1
Grain Elevator	MD	39.2283	-75.9908	4	4	0
Lamb's Knoll	MD	39.4483	-77.6258	4	1	3
Penn - DRL	PA	39.9522	-75.1887	4	1	3
Green Valley	PA	40.1544	-75.6857	4	3	1
SHNJ	NJ	40.4296	-73.9848	4	2	2
Phillips Exeter Academy	NH	42.9788	-70.9495	4	1	3
Great Bay Monarchs	NH	43.0752	-70.8394	4	0	4
Macdonald Campus of McGill University	QC	45.4079	-73.939	4	4	0
Deweese Island	SC	32.836	-79.7267	3	0	3
Cape Romain NWR, SC (HQ)	SC	32.9726	-79.6711	3	0	3
Fisherman's Island	VA	37.098	-75.9786	3	3	0
DWL Great Cypress Swamp	DE	38.4786	-75.3189	3	2	1
Kings Landing Park, Huntingtown	MD	38.6259	-76.6712	3	0	3
CHDE	DE	38.7703	-75.0852	3	3	0
Westtown School	PA	39.9482	-75.5383	3	1	2
Connex Village	PA	40.467	-76.6033	3	3	0
B10AOakTree	PA	40.4759	-76.6079	3	3	0
FRIS	NY	40.6328	-73.2157	3	3	0
Sherwood	CT	41.1121	-73.3305	3	1	2
Rome WMA	NY	43.1848	-75.5044	3	2	1
WNERR2	ME	43.3351	-70.5492	3	1	2
Pointe À la Loupe	QC	48.0766	-69.275	3	3	0
Grandes-Bergeronnes	QC	48.2581	-69.5214	3	3	0
Harbor Island	SC	32.3989	-80.4426	2	0	2
Captain Sams	SC	32.5828	-80.1401	2	0	2
The Sanctuary	SC	32.6012	-80.0921	2	0	2
Santee NWR, SC	SC	33.5338	-80.4313	2	2	0
SAVA03	VA	37.3222	-76.0077	2	2	0
Lupine Field	MD	38.3445	-75.4272	2	2	0
FORT	NJ	39.2225	-75.1661	2	1	1
Franklin Parker	NJ	39.7934	-74.4985	2	0	2
Downingtown Area School District at Marsh Creek	PA	40.0557	-75.7018	2	0	2
Middle Creek SGL	PA	40.2711	-76.2502	2	1	1
D8C	PA	40.4044	-76.6822	2	2	0
Rg27 Tower	PA	40.4086	-76.7116	2	2	0
A34 Repeater	PA	40.4443	-76.5965	2	2	0
B10A	PA	40.476	-76.6077	2	1	1
Big Pocono Fire Tower	PA	41.0424	-75.3526	2	1	1
MNTK	NY	41.0591	-71.8691	2	0	2
LUZE04	PA	41.1586	-76.1692	2	2	0
LACK04	PA	41.4494	-74.9915	2	2	0

Receiver name	Prov/State	Latitude°N	Longitude°W	Total	QC	NE
Zoo New England	MA	42.2225	-71.0621	2	0	2
Fort River	MA	42.3404	-72.5668	2	0	2
Lynnfield MS	MA	42.5376	-71.0517	2	0	2
Myers Point	NY	42.5381	-76.5488	2	2	0
Ipswich River Sanctuary	MA	42.631	-70.921	2	0	2
Capital District WMA	NY	42.6523	-73.3939	2	0	2
Albany Pine Bush Preserve Discovery Center	NY	42.7186	-73.8647	2	1	1
Greenwoods Conservancy	NY	42.7219	-75.1047	2	1	1
Strawberry Fields Preserve	NY	42.9245	-74.1238	2	2	0
Utica Zoo	NY	43.0823	-75.246	2	2	0
WNERR	ME	43.3351	-70.5492	2	2	0
Fassler	NY	43.368	-75.9094	2	2	0
Derby Hill Bird Observatory	NY	43.5276	-76.2389	2	2	0
Upper & Lower Lakes WMA	NY	44.6196	-75.2274	2	2	0
SUNY Potsdam - Bowman Hall	NY	44.6605	-74.9721	2	2	0
Magalloway	NH	45.0631	-71.1626	2	0	2
UdeSherbrooke	QC	45.3805	-71.9255	2	2	0
McGill_Bird_Observatory	QC	45.4307	-73.9385	2	2	0
Port-aux-Saumons	QC	47.759	-69.9457	2	2	0
Pointe-aux-Outardes4	QC	49.0433	-68.4606	2	2	0
Pointe-aux-Outardes3	QC	49.0433	-68.4603	2	2	0

Figure S1. Histograms of flight speed (km/hr, panel A, n = 103) and departure time (hours after sunset, Panel B, n = 50) of migratory flights made by tagged Rusty Blackbirds detected by Motus receivers.

Table S4. Summary of migratory stopovers made by Rusty Blackbirds affixed with NanoTags in New England (NE) and Observatoire d’oiseaux de Tadoussac, Québec (QC) including season, dates of first and last detections, duration in days, latitude and longitude of single receivers and mean latitude and longitude of multiple receivers that detected the stopover, tag identification number, and names of the Motus receivers that detected the stopover.

Season	Region	Start Date	End Date	Days	Latitude	Longitude	TagID	Receiver names
Fall	QC	2018-10-17	2018-10-22	5	47.4839	-69.9738	31883	St-Denis-sur-Mer, QC; Kamouraska, QC; Riviere-Ouelle, QC; St-Roch-des-Aulnaies, QC
Fall	QC	2020-10-03	2020-10-07	4	47.3340	-70.1464	49386	St-Roch-des-Aulnaies, QC; Riviere-Ouelle, QC
Fall	NE	2022-10-11	2022-10-15	4	44.8522	-73.2136	66476	Missisquoi Bay NWR, VT; Shelburne Farms, VT
Fall	QC	2020-10-05	2020-10-25	20	44.4423	-75.4760	49380	Upper & Lower Lakes WMA, NY; Perch River WMA, NY
Fall	NE	2018-10-14	2018-10-17	3	43.8651	-71.7137	NE GPS	
Fall	QC	2020-10-27	2020-11-07	11	43.1262	-75.3567	49382	Utica Zoo, NY; Rome WMA, NY
Fall	NE	2021-11-04	2021-11-07	3	42.3404	-72.5668	54699	Fort River, MA
Fall	NE	2018-10-20	2018-10-23	3	42.1400	-73.3823	NE GPS	
Fall	NE	2023-10-24	2023-10-26	2	41.9736	-71.1132	78307	Hockomock Swamp (E. S. Wilder WMA), MA
Fall	QC	2019-11-23	2019-11-25	2	41.3734	-71.5762	38522	TRUS, RI
Fall	QC	2019-11-13	2019-11-15	2	40.4059	-76.6922	38509	Rg27 Tower, PA; D8C_2, PA
Fall	QC	2020-11-07	2020-11-13	6	40.1276	-75.7690	48703	Marshlands 1, PA
Fall	QC	2020-11-17	2020-11-28	11	40.1276	-75.7690	48705	Marshlands 1, PA
Fall	NE	2021-11-03	2021-11-07	3	39.9035	-75.6894	54700	Westtown School, PA; Buck Run, PA; Bucktoe Preserve, PA
Fall	NE	2019-11-08	2019-11-12	4	39.8472	-75.6154	35157	Penn - DRL, PA; Bucktoe Preserve, PA
Fall	QC	2020-11-01	2020-11-04	3	39.7233	-75.5606	35059	DuPont Environmental Education Center, DE
Fall	NE	2022-10-31	2022-11-02	1	39.6905	-78.4067	66476	Town Hill Fire Tower, MD
Fall	NE	2021-11-11	2021-11-13	2	39.4483	-77.6258	54704	Lamb's Knoll, MD
Fall	QC	2020-11-07	2020-11-11	4	39.2283	-75.9908	35062	Grain Elevator, MD
Fall	QC	2021-10-28	2021-11-07	9	38.7718	-75.5676	35064	Redden SF, DE; Interstate Fire Tower, DE
Fall	QC	2019-11-09	2019-11-13	4	38.4460	-76.0919	38514	Blackwater NWR, MD
Fall	NE	2018-10-26	2018-11-04	9	38.4357	-76.9945	NE GPS	
Fall	QC	2020-11-14	2020-11-17	3	38.2507	-76.7020	35070	Newtowne Neck State Park, MD
Fall	NE	2023-11-07	2023-11-18	11	38.2000	-75.3887	78307	Nassawango Fire Tower, MD; Buntings, MD
Spring	QC	2018-04-25	2018-05-01	6	47.3109	-70.1677	25659	St-Roch-des-Aulnaies, QC
Spring	QC	2021-05-08	2021-05-15	8	43.1734	-75.4757	35026	Rome WMA, NY; Utica Zoo, NY

Season	Region	Start Date	End Date	Days	Latitude	Longitude	TagID	Receiver names
Spring	NE	2019-03-18	2019-03-30	12	41.0010	-74.6145	NE GPS	
Spring	NE	2020-03-28	2020-04-05	8	40.1276	-75.7690	35161	Marshlands 1, PA
Spring	QC	2021-04-12	2021-05-04	21	38.7738	-76.7113	35034	Patuxent River Park, MD
Spring	QC	2021-04-12	2021-04-19	6	38.7738	-76.7113	35064	Patuxent River Park, MD
Spring	NE	2022-04-01	2022-04-09	8	38.2507	-76.7020	54711	Newtowne Neck State Park, MD

Table S5. Summary of migratory flights of Rusty Blackbirds affixed with nano-transmitters in New England (NE) or Observatoire d’oiseaux de Tadoussac, Québec (QC), as detected by Motus receivers, including tag number, start and end times, coordinates of receivers (Latitude°N, and Longitude°W) for the first and last detections, season, capture site, flight duration (hrs), ground distance (km), estimated travel rate (km/hr), and bearing in degrees. Flights shorter than 75 km distance are not included due to space limitations. One flight estimated at a rate >250 km/hr was excluded from migration rate estimates; however, both detections appeared to be legitimate so we suspect the clock or time zone on one of the receivers may not have been accurate.

TagID	Start time	End time	Start Lat	Start Lon	End Lat	End Lon	Season	Site	hrs	km	km/hr	Bearing
35034	2021-11-10T03:15:56Z	2021-11-11T06:48:42Z	45.4079	-73.9390	39.7233	-75.5606	Fall	QC	27.6	645.3	23.4	192
78307	2023-11-06T01:56:33Z	2023-11-06T13:03:44Z	41.4787	-71.2438	37.0981	-75.9788	Fall	NE	11.1	634.9	57.1	222
54711	2021-11-04T03:13:51Z	2021-11-04T12:19:44Z	42.3404	-72.5668	38.7738	-76.7113	Fall	NE	9.1	529.1	58.2	223
35070	2021-11-05T04:29:23Z	2021-11-05T13:05:29Z	41.5530	-73.5236	38.2507	-76.7020	Fall	QC	8.6	456.3	53.1	218
35165	2019-11-02T05:02:39Z	2019-11-02T13:11:49Z	41.5530	-73.5236	38.2507	-76.7020	Fall	NE	8.2	456.3	56.0	218
35064	2020-10-30T23:25:28Z	2020-10-31T06:30:44Z	42.9245	-74.1238	39.2283	-75.9908	Fall	QC	7.1	439.4	62.0	202
35031	2020-11-12T14:24:47Z	2020-11-13T13:50:05Z	43.3680	-75.9094	40.0774	-78.7493	Fall	QC	23.4	435.2	18.6	214
78317	2023-10-13T00:46:04Z	2023-10-13T07:39:23Z	44.9443	-71.2087	41.0591	-71.8691	Fall	NE	6.9	435.0	63.1	187
78313	2023-11-06T02:33:42Z	2023-11-06T09:07:17Z	42.4617	-71.9032	39.8209	-75.7221	Fall	NE	6.6	434.4	66.2	229
54700	2022-03-31T02:47:48Z	2022-03-31T09:42:53Z	39.4483	-77.6258	42.7219	-75.1047	Spring	NE	6.9	420.7	60.8	29
38514	2019-10-09T02:21:55Z	2019-10-09T11:37:29Z	47.5154	-69.9502	43.9438	-71.7011	Fall	QC	9.3	419.7	45.3	200
66477	2022-10-27T19:53:22Z	2022-10-28T04:57:55Z	43.1848	-75.5044	40.9077	-79.4436	Fall	NE	9.1	412.6	45.5	234
25666	2017-11-07T01:00:03Z	2017-11-07T21:23:50Z	42.3633	-72.5123	39.9842	-75.4892	Fall	QC	20.4	363.6	17.8	224
35034	2020-11-12T04:47:48Z	2020-11-12T13:40:44Z	43.5276	-76.2389	40.4045	-76.6825	Fall	QC	8.9	348.8	39.3	186
54700	2021-11-03T02:56:00Z	2021-11-03T17:21:31Z	42.7186	-73.8647	39.9482	-75.5383	Fall	NE	14.4	338.1	23.4	205
35064	2021-04-19T01:35:37Z	2021-04-19T06:30:03Z	38.7738	-76.7113	41.0326	-74.9832	Spring	QC	4.9	291.1	59.3	30
35021	2020-10-08T07:16:23Z	2020-10-08T08:20:02Z	48.1232	-69.7168	46.0386	-67.8330	Fall	QC	1.1	272.3	256.7*	148

TagID	Start time	End time	Start Lat	Start Lon	End Lat	End Lon	Season	Site	hrs	km	km/hr	Bearing
66460	2022-10-28T04:14:20Z	2022-10-28T07:31:16Z	40.4107	-76.0796	38.6040	-78.1090	Fall	NE	3.3	265.9	81.0	222
54704	2021-11-11T02:29:28Z	2021-11-11T12:59:19Z	41.0424	-75.3526	39.4483	-77.6258	Fall	NE	10.5	262.2	25.0	228
54710	2021-11-04T22:34:52Z	2021-11-05T07:07:54Z	41.1121	-73.3305	39.1267	-74.8913	Fall	NE	8.6	257.5	30.1	212
35064	2021-10-28T07:20:05Z	2021-10-28T12:50:42Z	39.2225	-75.1661	37.0980	-75.9786	Fall	QC	5.5	246.3	44.7	197
49380	2020-11-14T03:47:36Z	2020-11-14T07:22:42Z	40.4107	-76.0796	38.2507	-76.7020	Fall	QC	3.6	245.7	68.5	193
35157	2019-11-12T23:51:51Z	2019-11-13T02:48:05Z	39.8209	-75.7221	37.7864	-76.3059	Fall	NE	2.9	231.5	78.8	193
54708	2021-11-06T03:54:33Z	2021-11-06T07:44:29Z	40.1544	-75.6857	38.2507	-76.7020	Fall	NE	3.8	228.9	59.7	203
35159	2019-11-02T06:13:59Z	2019-11-02T09:31:27Z	39.9842	-75.4892	38.2507	-76.7020	Fall	NE	3.3	219.2	66.6	209
78313	2023-10-13T00:45:00Z	2023-10-13T04:20:47Z	44.8716	-71.2254	42.9835	-71.3648	Fall	NE	3.6	210.1	58.4	183
35070	2021-04-21T02:45:45Z	2021-04-21T04:51:16Z	36.5270	-75.9894	38.2410	-75.1360	Spring	QC	2.1	204.7	97.8	21
48708	2021-03-31T04:28:13Z	2021-03-31T05:54:14Z	37.3205	-76.2788	39.0341	-75.6415	Spring	QC	1.4	198.2	138.3	16
66481	2022-10-28T02:57:12Z	2022-10-28T05:05:20Z	39.9522	-75.1887	38.6259	-76.6712	Fall	NE	2.1	195.0	91.3	221
48706	2020-10-11T22:57:14Z	2020-10-12T02:52:32Z	48.1591	-69.6623	46.8430	-71.2111	Fall	QC	3.9	187.2	47.7	219
48706	2020-10-25T03:38:26Z	2020-10-25T07:20:32Z	44.2176	-76.6069	42.5381	-76.5488	Fall	QC	3.7	186.7	50.4	179
25666	2017-09-27T00:37:18Z	2017-09-27T10:56:23Z	48.1406	-69.7190	46.8430	-71.2111	Fall	QC	10.3	182.9	17.7	218
35026	2021-05-08T02:59:35Z	2021-05-08T10:20:17Z	41.4494	-74.9915	43.0823	-75.2460	Spring	QC	7.4	182.6	24.9	353
66462	2022-11-03T10:07:34Z	2022-11-03T14:43:42Z	39.9842	-75.4892	38.6259	-76.6712	Fall	NE	4.6	182.0	39.6	214
54838	2021-10-06T04:13:04Z	2021-10-06T08:37:03Z	44.5136	-71.1872	42.9788	-70.9495	Fall	NE	4.4	171.6	39.0	174
35064	2021-04-12T02:17:51Z	2021-04-12T22:47:53Z	37.3205	-76.2788	38.7738	-76.7113	Spring	QC	20.5	165.7	8.1	347
66476	2023-04-13T03:14:21Z	2023-04-13T10:49:28Z	38.6259	-76.6712	39.9415	-75.8077	Spring	NE	7.6	164.0	21.6	27
78312	2023-10-29T07:00:52Z	2023-10-29T09:05:44Z	39.9842	-75.4892	39.0274	-76.7974	Fall	NE	2.1	154.7	74.4	227
35070	2021-09-30T02:27:03Z	2021-09-30T04:28:19Z	49.0433	-68.4606	47.8756	-69.5503	Fall	QC	2.0	152.8	75.6	212
35164	2019-11-13T00:49:47Z	2019-11-13T02:54:39Z	38.4460	-76.0919	37.0987	-76.3551	Fall	NE	2.1	151.3	72.7	189
54706	2021-11-20T03:48:42Z	2021-11-20T05:46:18Z	39.0341	-75.6415	37.7864	-76.3059	Fall	NE	2.0	150.2	76.6	203
35034	2021-05-14T06:21:00Z	2021-05-14T11:07:59Z	43.3680	-75.9094	44.6196	-75.2274	Spring	QC	4.8	149.4	31.2	21
49380	2020-09-21T05:29:09Z	2020-09-21T09:28:17Z	48.1406	-69.7190	47.0719	-70.7852	Fall	QC	4.0	143.3	36.0	214
54701	2021-10-28T01:53:23Z	2021-10-28T03:43:43Z	39.2225	-75.1661	38.7738	-76.7113	Fall	NE	1.8	142.8	77.7	250
35034	2021-09-29T07:06:36Z	2021-09-29T09:26:17Z	49.0433	-68.4606	48.1232	-69.7168	Fall	QC	2.3	138.1	59.3	223
54701	2021-10-08T01:07:51Z	2021-10-08T05:44:15Z	44.8716	-71.2254	43.6586	-71.5891	Fall	NE	4.6	137.9	29.9	192
35163	2019-11-13T02:43:08Z	2019-11-13T05:30:00Z	38.7421	-75.4146	37.7864	-76.3059	Fall	NE	2.8	131.7	47.4	217
35156	2019-11-09T04:12:07Z	2019-11-09T05:38:40Z	41.5530	-73.5236	40.4296	-73.9848	Fall	NE	1.4	130.7	90.6	197

TagID	Start time	End time	Start Lat	Start Lon	End Lat	End Lon	Season	Site	hrs	km	km/hr	Bearing
31417	2018-09-30T00:17:24Z	2018-09-30T02:41:37Z	47.5675	-69.8567	46.8430	-71.2111	Fall	QC	2.4	130.5	54.3	232
35161	2020-04-05T03:04:00Z	2020-04-05T05:16:08Z	40.3201	-75.9026	41.2997	-75.1247	Spring	NE	2.2	127.1	57.7	31
35156	2019-11-28T23:47:10Z	2019-11-29T01:47:03Z	38.4460	-76.0919	37.3205	-76.2788	Fall	NE	2.0	126.0	63.1	188
35164	2020-03-30T02:33:39Z	2020-03-30T03:30:18Z	38.2507	-76.7020	38.4786	-75.3189	Spring	NE	0.9	123.5	130.8	78
66476	2022-11-02T01:19:56Z	2022-11-02T02:47:34Z	39.6905	-78.4067	38.6040	-78.1090	Fall	NE	1.5	123.3	84.4	168
38515	2019-09-30T02:45:00Z	2019-09-30T04:10:03Z	47.5154	-69.9502	46.8430	-71.2111	Fall	QC	1.4	121.3	85.6	232
48705	2020-10-21T06:33:43Z	2020-10-21T09:42:42Z	47.5154	-69.9502	46.8430	-71.2111	Fall	QC	3.2	121.3	38.5	232
25659	2018-05-01T23:13:51Z	2018-05-02T03:06:55Z	47.3109	-70.1677	48.0766	-69.2750	Spring	QC	3.9	108.3	27.9	38
78312	2023-10-14T06:16:46Z	2023-10-14T07:55:23Z	42.6523	-73.3939	41.8318	-73.9420	Fall	NE	1.6	101.8	61.9	207
35062	2020-10-12T00:27:13Z	2020-10-12T02:23:25Z	48.1591	-69.6623	47.3109	-70.1677	Fall	QC	1.9	101.6	52.5	202
31421	2018-10-01T04:34:37Z	2018-10-01T07:49:51Z	48.1406	-69.7190	47.3109	-70.1677	Fall	QC	3.3	98.2	30.2	200
35060	2020-10-11T03:16:30Z	2020-10-11T04:53:01Z	48.1232	-69.7168	47.3109	-70.1677	Fall	QC	1.6	96.4	60.0	201
35064	2020-10-08T23:37:05Z	2020-10-09T01:40:54Z	48.1232	-69.7168	47.3109	-70.1677	Fall	QC	2.1	96.4	46.7	201
35164	2019-11-21T07:24:53Z	2019-11-21T08:39:38Z	32.9726	-79.6711	32.3989	-80.4426	Fall	NE	1.3	96.4	77.3	229
35155	2019-11-18T06:44:40Z	2019-11-18T08:33:56Z	31.8406	-81.0883	31.1229	-81.4776	Fall	NE	1.8	87.8	48.2	205
66476	2023-04-15T04:37:07Z	2023-04-15T06:00:36Z	42.1477	-73.4559	42.9200	-73.2390	Spring	NE	1.4	87.6	63.0	12
48700	2021-04-27T06:51:05Z	2021-04-27T08:00:52Z	38.2507	-76.7020	39.0274	-76.7974	Spring	QC	1.2	86.6	74.5	355
38517	2019-11-08T14:42:22Z	2019-11-08T17:34:24Z	41.1586	-76.1692	40.4670	-76.6033	Fall	QC	2.9	85.1	29.7	206
78307	2023-10-23T05:37:49Z	2023-10-23T11:11:27Z	42.9788	-70.9495	42.2225	-71.0621	Fall	NE	5.6	84.5	15.2	186
54711	2022-04-14T05:14:27Z	2022-04-14T06:10:30Z	41.0413	-74.2562	41.5530	-73.5236	Spring	NE	0.9	83.6	89.5	47
35038	2020-10-25T00:09:37Z	2020-10-25T01:32:36Z	48.1232	-69.7168	47.4266	-70.0611	Fall	QC	1.4	81.6	59.0	199
35034	2021-05-04T02:56:01Z	2021-05-04T03:28:49Z	38.7738	-76.7113	39.2283	-75.9908	Spring	QC	0.6	80.3	146.8	51
35032	2020-10-11T23:15:01Z	2020-10-12T00:40:57Z	47.8756	-69.5503	47.3109	-70.1677	Fall	QC	1.4	78.1	54.5	217
35072	2020-10-12T00:31:26Z	2020-10-12T01:53:08Z	47.8756	-69.5503	47.3109	-70.1677	Fall	QC	1.4	78.1	57.4	217
35064	2021-10-24T00:20:40Z	2021-10-24T01:56:21Z	42.4073	-71.3317	41.8731	-71.9450	Fall	QC	1.6	78.1	49.0	221
35034	2020-11-24T03:12:21Z	2020-11-24T03:52:59Z	37.7864	-76.3059	37.0987	-76.3551	Fall	QC	0.7	76.5	112.9	183
38514	2019-11-13T04:28:55Z	2019-11-13T05:27:51Z	38.4460	-76.0919	37.7864	-76.3059	Fall	QC	1.0	75.6	77.0	194

Table S6. Model selection table for the GAMM of latitude by date for Rusty Blackbirds affixed with nano-transmitters at two capture sites, including the number of parameters (k), AICc value, delta AICc, model likelihood (ModelLik), AICc weight, log likelihood (LL), and cumulative weight (Cum.Wt). The smooth interaction term for date by capture site, s(Site), was highly explanatory, suggesting that birds from the two capture sites had different migratory strategies. The random effect for repeated detections of each individual bird, s(tagID, fs), was most explanatory when fit as a factor smooth, rather than as a random intercept, s(tagID, re), or random slope, s(tagID, julian, re). The continuous temporal autoregression correlation structure at lag one was also highly explanatory (CAR1). The random effect for year, s(Year, re), was not explanatory and was not included in the final model.

Model	K	AICc	Delta_AICc	ModelLik	AICcWt	LL	Cum.Wt
s(Site) + s(tagID, fs) + CAR1	8	2511.11	0.00	1.00	0.36	-1247.50	0.36
s(Site) + s(tagID, fs) + s(Year, re) + CAR1	9	2511.31	0.20	0.90	0.32	-1246.59	0.68
s(Site) + s(tagID, fs) + s(Year, Julian, re) + CAR1	9	2511.31	0.20	0.90	0.32	-1246.59	1.00
s(Site) + s(Year, re) + CAR1	7	2540.22	29.12	0.00	0.00	-1263.07	1.00
s(Site) + s(tagID, re) + s(Year, re) + CAR1	8	2542.25	31.14	0.00	0.00	-1263.07	1.00
s(Site) + s(tagID, julian, re) + s(Year, re) + CAR1	8	2542.25	31.14	0.00	0.00	-1263.07	1.00
Site + s(tagID, fs) + s(Year, re) + CAR1	7	2545.83	34.72	0.00	0.00	-1265.87	1.00
s(tagID, fs) + s(Year, re) + CAR1	6	2629.20	118.09	0.00	0.00	-1308.57	1.00
s(Site) + s(tagID, fs) + s(Year, re)	8	3111.25	600.14	0.00	0.00	-1547.57	1.00

Table S7. Model selection table for the GAMM of latitude by date, age, and sex for Rusty Blackbirds affixed with nano-transmitters at two capture sites, including the number of parameters (k), AICc value, delta AICc, model likelihood (ModelLik), AICc weight, log likelihood (LL), and cumulative weight (Cum.Wt). All models in this table included the terms in the top model from Table S6.

Model	K	AICc	Delta_AICc	ModelLik	AICcWt	LL	Cum.Wt
s(Sex)	11	2294.50	0.00	1.00	0.45	-1136.13	0.45
s(Sex) + s(Year, re)	12	2294.51	0.01	0.99	0.44	-1135.11	0.89
s(Sex) + s(Age)	14	2298.71	4.21	0.12	0.05	-1135.17	0.94
s(Sex) + s(Age) + s(Year, re)	15	2299.09	4.59	0.10	0.04	-1134.33	0.99
Null	8	2302.42	7.93	0.02	0.01	-1143.15	1.00
Sex + Age + s(Year, re)	11	2306.26	11.76	0.00	0.00	-1142.01	1.00
s(Age)	11	2308.25	13.75	0.00	0.00	-1143.01	1.00

Figure S2. Predicted values and 95% confidence intervals from the top GAMM model in Table S7, for latitude by date of Rusty Blackbirds affixed with nano-transmitters at capture sites in New England (NE, top) and Observatoire d’oiseaux de Tadoussac, Québec (QC, bottom). There was some evidence that males (orange) from both populations wintered at higher latitudes than females (purple), though Motus detections at wintering latitudes were limited.